

Plant population requirement of hybrid rice in the Tarai region of Uttar Pradesh, India

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We conducted field experiments to evaluate the effect of plant density on yield of hybrid rice during the 1996-97 wet seasons at the GBPUAT Crop Research Centre. A split-plot design, with 20 × 20 cm and 15 × 15-cm spacing in the main plot and 1, 2, and 3 seedlings hill⁻¹ in the subplot, was used with four replications. Promising hybrid variety PRH1 (128 d) (1996) and recently released Pant Sankar Dhan-1 (118 d) (1997) were used.

Nurseries were sown on 12 June and transplanting began on 12 July in both years. The crop was fertilized with 175 - 26.4 - 33 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Half of the N and the full P and K were applied basally before

transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed, at tillering and at panicle initiation. The crop was sprayed with 0.5% ZnSO₄ + 0.25% slaked lime in water, twice (10 and 20 d after transplanting, [DAT]) in the nursery and once in the main field (15 DAT). The soil was silt loam (Aquic Hapludoll) with pH 8.0, 1.1% organic C, 20 kg available P ha⁻¹, and cation exchange capacity of 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil.

Dense transplanting at 15 × 15-cm spacing was superior to normal spacing (20 × 20 cm), but the difference in yield was significant only in 1996. The higher yields (8.3% in 1996 and 7.4% in 1997) under close spacing were associated with signifi-

cantly increased panicle numbers and total spikelets m⁻² (see table).

The recommended 2 seedlings hill⁻¹ for inbred rice varieties was optimum even for these hybrids. Transplanting with 2 or 3 seedlings hill⁻¹ increased the number of panicles and total spikelets. This increase was significant in both years, except for total spikelets in 1997.

Results showed no indication of reduced plant density under experimental conditions. A yield advantage of 0.5 t ha⁻¹ for close transplanting at 15 × 15 cm may compensate for the high seed cost of hybrid rice.

Effect of seedling number and spacing on grain yield, harvest index, and yield components of hybrid rice, GBPUAT, Pantnagar, India, 1996-97.

Treatment	PRHI (1996)							Pant Sankar Dhan-I (1997)						
	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Spikelets			1,000-grain wt (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Spikelets			1,000-grain wt (g)
				Total m ⁻² (no. × 1,000)	Filled panicles (no.)	Unfilled (%)					Total m ⁻² (no. × 1,000)	Filled panicles (no.)	Unfilled (%)	
<i>Plant spacing</i>														
20 × 20 cm	6.0	0.52	246	29.1	98	18	24.8	5.4	0.48	245	35.3	105	28	24.3
15 × 15 cm	6.5	0.52	301	35.0	97	19	24.8	5.8	0.49	270	40.2	108	28	23.9
SE±	0.1	0.002	6	0.8	5	1	0.1	0.1	0.002	5	0.6	4	1	0.2
LSD (5%)	0.3	ns ^a	26	3.6	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	22	2.7	ns	ns	ns
CV (5%)	4.0	1.33	7	9.0	16	11	1.0	7.0	1.56	7	5.5	12	9	3
<i>Seedling number hill⁻¹</i>														
1	5.9	0.53	229	30.7	109	19	24.7	5.4	0.49	241	36.5	111	27	24.4
2	6.4	0.52	286	31.5	96	17	24.7	5.7	0.49	261	37.9	106	26	24.0
3	6.5	0.52	1	33.9	88	19	24.8	5.8	1.49	271	38.9	101	29	24.0
SE±	0.1	0.004	10	7.5	4	1	0.1	0.1	0.003	6	0.6	3	1	0.2
LSD (5%)	0.4	ns	30	1.6	13	ns	ns	0.3	ns	18	ns	ns	ns	ns
CV (%)	6.0	2.17	10	5.0	11	16	11	5.0	2.01	6	5.0	9	11	2

^ans = not significant.

Promising medium-duration varieties for double-cropped areas of Assam

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Most rice-growing areas in Assam, India, are monocropped. Farmers grow long-duration varieties (140–160 d) in areas

where land becomes unsuitable to take up rabi (wet season) crops because of moisture stress and cold environmental condi-

tions after rice harvest. This is why most cultivable land remains fallow after sali (June/July–November/December) rice.

Rice cultivars with medium duration (130 d) are needed to grow rabi crops after fallow and thus increase cropping intensity.

Using pedigree selection methods, we developed two medium-duration varieties, Satya and Basundhara, from crosses IET9711/IET11162 and IET9711/IET11161, respectively. They can be sown in June and harvested in October. Both varieties take about 130 d from seed to seed so that rice fields are cleared by October to facilitate early tillage operations for the timely sowing of rabi crops. Table 1 shows the salient features of the two varieties.

Satya and Basundhara were resistant and moderately resistant to several insect pests and diseases, except bacterial leaf blight (BLB) and sheath blight of rice. They should not be planted in BLB-endemic areas. No other popular variety, however, is resistant to sheath blight in the state. Satya and Basundhara can replace existing varieties as a follow up rabi crop.

The varieties were tested at four locations in 1994 and in farmers' fields in Assam in 1997. They were also included under the All-India Testing and Frontline Block Demonstration Programme in Assam. Table 2 shows the performance data on these varieties at various locations. Although yields of Satya and Basundhara were not exceptionally higher than those of popular long-duration varieties, their shorter growth duration makes them ideal for growing before the rabi season.

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Table 1. Salient features of Satya and Basundhara at RARS, Titabar, Assam, India.

Feature	Satya	Basundhara	Control (Mahsuri)
Cross	IET9711/IET11162	IET9711/IET11161	(Mayong Ebos 80/ Taichung 65)/Mayong Ebos 80
Designation	TTB148-169-2-1-1	TTB149-121-5-1-1	Check
Days to 50% flowering	100	100	115
Plant height (cm)	113	107	140
Flag leaf size (cm)	36 × 1.5	33 × 1.6	43.5 × 2.0
Leaf collar	Green	Green	Light green
Tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	8-10	8-10	8-10
Panicle type	Compact	Compact	Compact
Panicle length (cm)	21	23	26
Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	160	170	284
Threshability	Intermediate	Intermediate	Shattering
Kernel length (mm)	4.76	4.78	5.70
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.64	2.04	2.20
Length/breadth (L/B)	2.90	2.34	2.59
1,000-grain wt (g)	19.6	24.0	16.2
Endosperm type	Nonglutinous	Nonglutinous	Nonglutinous
Kernel color	White	White	White
Abdominal white	Absent	Trace	Absent
Hulling (%)	78	75	75
Milling (%)	64	62	62
Head rice recovery (%)	63	60	60
Seed dormancy	Nondormant	Nondormant	Nondormant
Photoperiod sensitivity	Insensitive	Insensitive	Insensitive
Disease reaction ^a			
Blast	MR	MR	S
Bacterial leaf blight	S	S	MR
Sheath blight	S	S	S
Insect reaction ^a			
Stem borer	MR	MR	MR
Gall midge	R	R	MS
Brown planthopper	R	R	S
Whitebacked planthopper	R	R	S
Leaf folder	MR	MR	MR

^aMR = moderately resistant, R = resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Mean yield (t ha⁻¹) of Satya and Basundhara under various trials, India, 1994-97^a.

Location	Check					
	Satya	Basundhara	Jaya	Mahsuri	Ratna	LSD 5%
Within state (1994)						
RARS, Titabar	4.6	5.2	3.9	3.6		0.5
FTS, Nagaon	4.9	5.2	4.3	4.3		0.8
FTS, Sukliboria	4.2	4.2	3.9	4.0		0.8
FTS, Gerua	2.7	2.3	2.3	2.7		0.4
Mean	4.1	4.2	3.6	3.6		-
Farmers' fields (1997)						
Mohimabari (Jorhat)	5.1	5.0		3.0		
Bherbheri (Nagaon)	5.0	4.8		3.5		
Dalgaon (Darrang)	4.2	4.0		3.1		
Dhekiajuli (Sonitpur)	3.9	3.8		2.9		
Mean	4.5	4.4		3.1		
All India trials (1996)						
Bhubaneswar	3.6	5.5	3.3		4.8	0.8
Joypur	5.9	4.9	3.6		4.8	0.9
Ciplima	4.4	5.4	4.3		3.3	0.6
Patna	5.6	4.5	5.4		5.2	0.8
Chinsurah	4.0	3.0	3.0		3.5	0.6
Pusa	3.5	4.3	4.3		3.5	ns
Masodha	3.4	6.0	5.5		3.6	1.2
Jagdapur	2.9	3.6	3.4		-	0.7
Raipur	4.1	3.7	3.5		3.7	0.6
Mean	4.2	4.5	4.0		4.0	-

^aRARS = Regional Agricultural Research Station, ns = not significant.